

Studies in the Cotarnine Series. Part I. Action of Phenyl *iso*Cyanate and Phenyl *iso*Thiocyanate on Cotarnine.

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The commonly accepted formulæ for cotarnine admit of three tautomeric types, *viz.*, the aldehyde-imine (I), the carbinol (II), and the ammonium hydroxide (III).

Roser (*Annalen*, 1888, 249, 156; 1889, 254, 334) assigned to the free base formula (I) and to its hydrochloride the formula of an ammonium chloride derived from (III). That cotarnine was a secondary base as implied in structure (I) was inferred from its reaction with methyl iodide, two methyl groups being taken up in the formation of the quaternary iodide. Evidence of the presence of a free aldehyde group was derived from a study of the action of hydroxylamine both on the free base and on its benzoyl derivative. The easy oxidation to cotarnine of hydrocotarnine which, from its chemical behaviour, cannot have any other structure than (IV), is, however, admittedly difficult of explanation on the basis of Roser's formula, although the reverse change, the reduction of cotarnine to hydrocotarnine, might be readily accounted for.

The formula failed also to explain the relationship to cotarnine of certain of its derivatives such as the tarconines and Decker (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1893, 47, 222) indicated other difficulties in the way of acceptance of Roser's open-chain structure and proposed to substitute for it the carbinol formula (II). This view met with general approval and Hantzsch and Kalb (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3109) who investigated the conductivities of solutions of cotarnine cyanide and cotarnine hydrochloride, suggested that such solutions consisted of a mixture in equilibrium probably of Decker's carbinol form and the ammonium hydroxide form.

The spectroscopic investigations (Dobbie, Lauder and Tinkler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 598) have favoured the conclusion that cotarnine has normally the carbinol formula but changes rapidly in aqueous or alcoholic solution into the ammonium hydroxide, yielding ultimately an equilibrium mixture of the two. Hantzsch and Kalb (*loc. cit.*) represent cotarnine cyanide as a derivative of the carbinol form (V).

Freund and Becker (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1521) who obtained *norcotarnine* by the decomposition of cotarnine anilmethiodide, considered the reaction to be explained best by assuming the aldehyde constitution for cotarnine, while Liebermann, Kropf and Glawe (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 211, 2738) have suggested two alternative structures (VI and VII), derived from either the aldehydic or carbinol forms, for the products obtained by condensing cotarnine with ketones and ketonic bodies containing the $-\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$ grouping, thus:—

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

Hope and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 1168; 2114) and Robinson and Robinson (*ibid.*, 1913, 103, 372; 1914, 105, 1456) who have studied the reaction between cotarnine and nitromethane and also between cotarnine and aromatic nitro bodies containing a reactive methylene group, have assigned the closed ring formulæ to the products and expressed the view that cotarnine existed normally in the aldehydic form which changed during the reaction into the carbinol form, a molecule of water being subsequently eliminated from the latter, thus:

(VIII)

It seems clear, therefore, that the evidence on which the present conflicting views about the structure of cotarnine are based is far from satisfactory and the investigation of such reactions as might be interpreted without the least ambiguity in support of a definite constitution for this base would be desirable. In the present communication we have examined very fully the reactions of cotarnine with phenyl isocyanate and phenyl isothiocyanate and the results of our investigation have furnished a convincing proof of the aldehydic structure for this base.

The reactions which occur at the ordinary temperature and with quantitative yields of products may be expected to give rise to either a urea or a urethane derivative, according as we accept structures (I) or (II) for cotarnine, thus:—

That the urea constitution (IX) is the only one that is tenable would be obvious from the following considerations: (i) it is completely insoluble in dilute acids which could hardly have been the case with a compound of the urethane structure in which the basic $-N\cdot Me$ group remains free; (ii) it reacts smoothly with hydroxylamine to form a crystalline monoxime showing the presence of a free aldehyde group. The oxime is quite stable, dissolves unchanged in cold alkalis and is readily acetylated and benzoylated giving monoacyl derivatives which are insoluble in alkali. Moreover, the oxime is found to react again with phenyl isocyanate to form the urethanourea derivative (XIII), the oximinohydroxyl group being evidently involved in the reaction. The same compound has been synthesised from cotarnine oxime and phenyl isocyanate, the various reactions being explained by the scheme given below:—

Fresh evidence of the existence of a free aldehyde group in cotarnomethylphenylurea is derived from its reaction with the toluidines (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) which condense, on gently warming the components, to crystalline toluidils of the following type:—

(XIV)

The curious observation was made that when the same reaction was carried out with aniline, carbanilide was the only product that could be isolated. The reaction presumably takes place according to the following scheme:

The series of reactions mentioned above has also been carried out with phenyl isothiocyanate, the resulting cotarnomethylphenylthiourea and its derivatives being similar in all respects to the simple ureas.

Should cotarnine have the carbinol formula it is difficult to conceive of any valid reason why the alcoholic group should not have reacted immediately to produce non-aldehydic urethanes differing fundamentally in their chemical behaviour from the aldehydic ureas

which were actually obtained. It seems to us that the reactions of cotarnine with phenyl isocyanate and phenyl isothiocyanate do not admit of any other interpretations than those given above and they constitute, therefore, fresh and clear evidence in favour of the aldehyde-imine structure for this base.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cotarnomethylphenylurea (IX).—Cotarnine (2 g.) which has been freshly prepared, dried and powdered was suspended in dry benzene (12 c.c.) and phenyl isocyanate (2 c. c.) quickly added and the mixture shaken. The mixture momentarily became clear and immediately after crystals of the new product began to separate. These were collected, washed thrice with small quantities of cold benzene and dried in the desiccator. It forms colourless rectangular prisms melting sharply at 137° , yield 2.4 g. It is perfectly insoluble in dilute hydrochloric acid, cold or warm. (Found: C, 63.6; H, 5.6; N, 7.96. $C_{19}H_{20}O_5N_2$ requires C, 64.0; H, 5.6; N, 7.86 per cent).

The *oxime* (XI).—The powdered urea (1.6 g.) was suspended in dry alcohol (10 c. c.), warmed to 50° and quickly treated with a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.6 g.) and crystallised sodium acetate (1.6 g.) in 4 c. c. water. On stirring for a few minutes crystals of the oxime separated in glistening colourless plates, m. p. 152° (decomp.), yield 1.7 g. It dissolves slowly in cold caustic soda with a pale yellow colour and is reprecipitated unchanged on the addition of acids or passing CO_2 into the solution. (Found: C, 60.9; H, 5.48; N, 11.14. $C_{19}H_{21}O_5N_3$ requires C, 61.46; H, 5.66; N, 11.32 per cent).

Action of phenyl isocyanate on the oxime of cotarnomethylphenylurea: Phenylurethane of cotarnomethylphenylurea oxime (XIII).—The oxime (0.6 g.) was suspended in dry benzene (10 c. c.), phenyl isocyanate (1 c. c.) added and the mixture warmed on the water-bath to about 50° , when the flask was soon filled with crystals. Crystallisation from hot alcohol gave colourless plates, m. p. 151° . The same compound was obtained in almost theoretical yield when cotarnine oxime, suspended in dry benzene, was treated with phenylisocyanate, m. p. 151° , proved to be identical with the previous compound by a mixed m. p. (Found: C, 63.2; H, 5.2; N, 11.62. $C_{26}H_{26}O_6N_4$ requires C, 63.7; H, 5.3; N, 11.43 per cent).

Acetylation of the oxime of cotarnomethylphenylurea (XII).—The oxime (0.6 g.) was treated with 10 drops of freshly distilled acetic anhydride and gently warmed on the water-bath until there was a clear yellow solution. The cold solution was rubbed with a few drops of 2*N*-alkali and the separating granular solid washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless prismatic needles, m. p. 139°. (Found: C, 61.2; H, 5.5; N, 10.15. $C_{21}H_{23}O_6N_3$ requires C, 61.0; H, 5.57; N, 10.17 per cent).

Benzoylation of the oxime of cotarnomethylphenylurea.—The oxime (1 g.) was dissolved in excess of 2*N*-alkali and the solution rubbed vigorously in a mortar with 1 c. c. of benzoyl chloride until the oil completely solidified. After washing with alkali and crystallising from alcohol it was obtained in long colourless plates, m. p. 142°. (Found: N, 8.88. $C_{26}H_{25}O_6N_3$ requires N, 8.82 per cent.).

Condensation of Cotarnomethylphenylurea with Aromatic Amines.

(a) *Aniline.*—The urea (1 g.) was mixed with freshly distilled aniline (2 c. c.) and stirred until it dissolved. On keeping the solution overnight at room temperature needle-shaped crystals were found to be deposited which were identified as carbanilide (m. p. 238°) by m. p. and mixed m. p. determination.

(b) *p-Toluidine.*—Molecular quantities were dissolved in the minimum amount of alcohol, mixed and warmed gently and allowed to stand overnight. The solid, which separated, crystallised from hot alcohol in colourless needles which changed colour at 135° and melted at 168°. (Found: N, 9.62. $C_{26}H_{27}O_4N_3$ requires N, 9.43 per cent).

(c) *o-Toluidine.*—The oil, which separated on diluting the alcoholic solution, was treated with dilute acetic acid when it solidified. Crystallisation from alcohol gave small colourless needles, m. p. 196°. (Found: N, 9.58. $C_{26}H_{27}O_4N_3$ requires N, 9.43 per cent).

(d) *m-Toluidine.*—The product was obtained in the same way as that from *o*-toluidine. Long prismatic needles, m. p. 168°. (Found: N, 9.7. $C_{26}H_{27}O_4N_3$ requires N, 9.43 per cent).

Action of phenyl isothiocyanate on cotarnine: cotarnomethylphenylthiourea.—Finely powdered cotarnine (1 g.), suspended in dry benzene (8 c. c.), was treated with phenyl isothiocyanate (1 c. c.) and the mixture stirred and warmed until a clear solution was obtained. On cooling in ice the thiourea separated out quantitatively in shining crystals from excess of hot benzene as flat needles, m. p. 132°.

depressed by admixture with cotarnine to 116° . It is completely insoluble in cold dilute acids. (Found: C, 61.68; H, 5.5; N, 7.8. $C_{19}H_{20}O_4N_2S$ requires C, 61.3; H, 5.4; N, 7.5 per cent).

The *oxime* was prepared in precisely the same way as the urea oxime. It crystallised from alcohol in lustrous rhombic plates, m. p. 142° . It dissolves in dilute caustic soda only on warming and is reprecipitated on acidification. (Found: N, 10.9. $C_{19}H_{21}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 10.85 per cent). The hydroxyl group of the oxime is apparently non-reactive towards phenyl isothiocyanate, for neither the urea nor the thiourea oximes could be made to condense with this reagent to form the desired urethane derivatives, only unchanged material being recovered at the end.

The *acetyl* derivative of the thiourea oxime, prepared in the usual way, crystallises from alcohol in stellate clusters of needles, m. p. 147° , insoluble in alkali. (Found: N, 9.89. $C_{21}H_{23}O_5N_3S$ requires N, 9.79 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative crystallises from a large excess of boiling alcohol in thin plates, m. p. 153° . (Found: N, 8.7. $C_{26}H_{25}O_5N_3S$ requires, N, 8.55 per cent).

Cotarnomethylphenylthiourea anil.—The clear solution, obtained on mixing molecular proportions of aniline and the thiourea and warming to 40° on the water-bath, was cooled and treated with a few drops of dilute acetic acid and rubbed vigorously. The oily product soon solidified and was washed with alcohol and crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether as needles, m. p. 146° , mixed with thiocarbanilide the m. p. was depressed to 130° . (Found: N, 9.2. $C_{25}H_{25}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 9.39 per cent).

We desire to express our thanks to the Superintendent of the Govt. Opium Factory at Ghazipur for a kind gift of pure narcotine which was used in this investigation.

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Received May 26, 1934.